

Building a Low-cost Cloud Native 5G Network Slicing Experimental Testbed: Open-Source Solutions, Lessons Learned and Future Directions

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Abstract—Research on network slicing has gained some ground since its introduction to 5G networking. Network slicing has evolved from ideas, concepts, and simulations to real-world implementations. With this advancement, the realization and experimentation of network slicing remain a challenge due to the complexity involved. Research and experimentation testbeds have been built to explore and advance network slicing. However, most are quite expensive to set up or complicated for the novice researcher exploring 5G network slicing. In this work, we present a comprehensive and repeatable methodology that can be used to realize network slicing. Our approach focuses on building a low-cost, experimental cloud-native testbed using open-source solutions. The testbed leverages containerization and orchestration platforms to deploy the core network. We demonstrate end-to-end network slicing by extending the Open Air Interface’s reference setup with custom Helm charts. We validate the process of the user equipment requesting a slice on the network, to admission and management of the slice using slice-specific identifiers like Slice Service Type and Slice Differentiator. We highlight the lessons learned when automating this testbed setup to ensure the testbed is repeatable, consistent and proper resource isolation is achieved per slice as envisioned in network slicing. This work serves as a practical guide for researchers to experiment with and explore network slicing using readily available off-the-shelf hardware.

Index Terms—5G, Network Slicing, Cloud Native, Testbed.

I. INTRODUCTION

The fifth generation of mobile networks (5G) promise a step-change in how connectivity is provisioned and monetised, particularly through network slicing, which

enables the creation of multiple, service-level agreement (SLA)-differentiated logical networks over a shared physical infrastructure comprising the radio access network (RAN), transport, and core components [1]. The RAN manages radio spectrum and wireless connectivity to user devices. The core network (CN) handles authentication, session management, and service orchestration, while the transport network (TN) provides high-capacity backhaul, midhaul, and fronthaul connectivity that interconnects these elements. In the African context, where operators must simultaneously extend coverage into sparsely populated or low-average revenue per user (ARPU) regions and unlock enterprise revenue to sustain capital and operational expenditures, slicing offers a pragmatic path to reuse infrastructure across verticals while guaranteeing performance isolation [2].

In 5G, three primary slices are defined, i.e., the ultra-reliable low latency communication (uRLLC), enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), and the massive machine type communication (mMTC). uRLLC enables mission-critical applications requiring sub-millisecond latency and 99.999% reliability such as industrial automation and autonomous vehicles, eMBB delivers high-throughput broadband services for applications like 4K/8K video streaming and virtual reality, while mMTC supports massive IoT deployments with millions of low-power, low-data-rate sensors and devices per square kilometre, such as IoT-enabled agriculture and smart metering. By so doing, one network build-out is turned into several

monetisable services, over logically separated and isolated network slices, each with distinct QoS requirements [3].

In the realm of experimentation, research and evaluation, E2E network slice implementations are considered complex and add-on services beyond what a basic E2E 5G network offers. Industry-scale testbeds have been built to advance wireless research in Europe and America. They cover city-wide deployment of wireless networks. Often, access to such industry scale testbeds, especially for the African researcher, is still a challenge. Smaller scale 5G mobile network testbeds like [4] [5] discuss low-cost deployment of 5G networks. Such testbeds accelerate capacity building for researchers who want to familiarize with 5G technology, and those with limited access to the industry-scale 5G equipment, or want to go beyond the abstraction provided by the large-scale testbed to fully understand the operation of complex 5G networks while solving practical problems [6]. Additionally, access to such lab-scale testbeds is key in prototyping and research of advanced 5G features that go beyond standard deployment and can later be extended to large wireless networks and very niche use cases. E2E 5G network slicing is one of these advanced features of the deployment of the 5G network. This is because of the complexity that comes with the logical separation and management of resources and access of the network across the different domains from the RAN, TN and CN. Esmaeily et al. [7] present a design criteria for setting up small scale 5G testbeds for network slicing. The key attributes defined and identified to set up a small testbed for network slicing are: Support for enabling technologies like software defined networking (SDN), network function virtualisation (NFV) and cloud computing that allows for flexible, dynamic and programmable orchestration of the network at different levels. The 5G testbed should offer multi-domain support that spans across the RAN, TN, and CN which in turn provides the possibility of offering E2E network slicing.

Open-source ecosystems like the OpenAirInterface (OAI) project, which comprises the OAI Core Network ¹ and OAI RAN ², along with software radio system (srs) RAN ³, and Open5GS ⁴ offer a disaggregated discussion that explains how network slicing can be achieved. Despite these software modules being among the popular open-source frameworks deployed in experimental research of 5G testbeds, they still fall short of offering a clear, detailed approach for implementing E2E 5G network slicing. OAI, in their documentation ⁵, give a scenario of 5G network slicing at the CN and possibilities of implementing slicing on the RAN, but a detailed explanation of how this can be configured and achieved in their newly built cloud native CN, that also takes in YAML configurations and is deployed using HELM package manager and K8 resource

¹<https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/cn5g>

²<https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/openairinterface5g>

³https://github.com/srsran/srsRAN_Project

⁴<https://github.com/open5gs/open5gs>

⁵https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/cn5g/oai-cn5g-fed/-/blob/master/docs/DEPLOY_SA5G_SLICING.md

orchestrator, remains limited and not very descriptive.

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to provide a practical approach of setting up a low cost experimental testbed for evaluating network slicing in 5G. We summarize the contribution of this work as follows:

- We describe the process of setting up a cloud native small-scale testbed for rapid research, experimentation, and capacity building using low-cost devices. In addition, we demonstrate the separation of the control plane and data planes in the testbed. The control plane handles all signaling, management, and session coordination functions, while the data plane is responsible for the actual data transmission including packet forwarding and quality of service control. In a 5G testbed environments, the separation of control and data planes allows for more granular testing, better resource utilization, and the ability to experiment with different deployment models that reflect real-world 5G network scenarios.
- We present the implementation steps that achieve 5G network slicing to showcase two user equipment assigned to dedicated slice. At its base, this work builds upon OAI configuration and design guides and extends the deployment of network slices by translating the docker compose methodology in ⁶ into helm charts to suit our custom slicing needs. Our approach aims to maintain simplicity while demonstrating and documenting the technical aspects of what is needed to implement and have an advanced automated cloud native 5G testbed.
- This work contributes to the broader Open6GNet⁷ initiative, which aims to develop open, programmable, and AI-enabled network architectures for 6G systems. The Open6GNet project envisions a future where network infrastructure is fully disaggregated, cloud-native, and capable of supporting advanced AI/ML-driven network management. Our testbed methodology aligns with Open6GNet's objectives by demonstrating practical implementations of cloud-native network slicing using open-source components, providing a foundation for researchers to explore programmable network architectures that will be essential for 6G evolution. The lessons learned from this 5G slicing testbed implementation directly inform the development of more advanced, AI-driven network orchestration mechanisms envisioned in the Open6GNet framework.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows; in section II, we highlight a background on the 5G reference architecture in relation to network slicing and the cloud native technology stack that can be used to realize network slicing. In section III, we present some of the research and works done in the topic of 5G testbeds and network slicing, which serve as a foundation on which this work is built. The description of steps involved to setup the testbed are discussed in section IV. In

⁶https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/cn5g/oai-cn5g-fed/-/blob/master/docs/DEPLOY_SA5G_SLICING.md

⁷<https://www.open6gnet.org/>

section V, we validate the realization of network slicing on the testbed, and in section VI we highlight key lessons learned in the implementation, and thereafter we provide future research directions in section VII. Finally, we conclude this work in section VIII.

II. BACKGROUND

A. General 5G System architecture in the context of Network Slicing.

The 5G system includes the 5G CN and 5G RAN that are interconnected by the N2 and N3 interfaces. The N2 interface is the entry point of the 5G RAN into the 5G Core via the access and management function (AMF). The N3 interface is the data plane that carries user traffic from the RAN through the CN and out to external Data Networks (DNs) via the N6 interface. Within the 5G CN, the different network functions expose a service based interface, which can be used by different CN functions to access the services provided by other NFs while also allowing multiple interactions among the NFs defined by a specific network slice [9].

It is important to note that the service-based architecture that the 5G CN employs for the different NFs is complemented by the implementation of NFs as VNFs, which allows software NFs to be implemented either as virtual machines and containers on Docker or Kubernetes.

The NRF provides and maintains the information of all the deployed NF instances to support service discovery. In the context of network slicing, the NSSF manages network slice selection and access to network slices in coordination with the AMF and the SMF via the N22 interface [9]. The Slice/Service Type (SST) and Session Description (SD) identifiers are crucial in a 5G network to ensure that slices are described, configured and isolated [10], [11]. 3GPP defines SST values as 1 for eMBB, 2 for URLLC, and 3 for mMTC, with 4–127 reserved and 128–255 operator-specific [12], while the SD is a 24-bit value that distinguishes slices of the same SST, ensuring the SST+SD pair uniquely identifies a network slice instance. They also act as identifiers that can be paired with a DNN value to ensure strict isolation on network slices at the CN. Furthermore, as noted by Limani et al [11], slice isolation can be achieved by allocating both physical and logical resources for a slice. For instance, the SMF, which is responsible for UE IP allocation, UPF selection and session management, can be configured to only issue an IP address pool to a specific DNN per slice to ensure logical isolation of traffic at the CN over distinct networks.

The 5G CN can also be separated into the control plane and data plane. The control plane carries control plane information and signalling messages while the data plane carries user traffic [10]. A comprehensive 5G system architecture with the associated interfaces and their interaction is shown in Figure

B. Cloud Native Technology Stack Supporting 5G Network Slicing

In 5G network slicing, orchestrating and managing logical networks on top of a shared physical infrastructure requires flexibility and efficiency [13]. This flexibility in network slicing use cases means service elasticity, service upgrade and update to support the life cycle of a network slice. This life cycle involves slice creation, execution, monitoring and termination [13]. This flexibility and elasticity in the context of 5G networking can be achieved by softwarization, virtualisation, and cloud computing technologies supporting the deployment of 5G network functions.

A few technologies have been used to aid the deployment and management of 5G network functions. Infrastructure management, from bare metal to initial configuration and setup, can be managed and automated through Infrastructure as Code principles, for example using Ansible⁸. Ansible playbooks ensure that the infrastructure used to deploy 5G networks is idempotent, meaning running the same playbook multiple times will give the same results. In the case of 5G testbeds, this ensures that a consistent desired state of the underlying testbed is maintained. A private 5G experimentation testbed built using infrastructure as code with Ansible is demonstrated in [14].

Beyond initial testbed set up and base configuration, 5G RAN and CN NFs need to be deployed and tied together to create an end-to-end 5G network. With softwarization of NFs, a cloud native approach with relevant tools can be used to implement network slicing. The design patterns of cloud native applications discussed in [15] involve containerization, where an application, in this case 5G NFs, are packaged as lightweight bundles of applications code, libraries, configuration and dependencies that ensures applications run consistently over different computing environments. Containerization can be achieved using tools such as Docker⁹ to build a Docker image using a Dockerfile [16]. In the realm of 5G NFs, there are a number of open source 5G network functions, from the RAN to the CN, that have been built and stored on different container registries such as Docker Hub¹⁰ including implementations from OAI¹¹ and Open5GS¹².

The next design pattern of cloud native applications that can support network slicing is the composition of microservices to create and serve an application [15]. In the context of network slicing, multiple container network functions must be interconnected to provide an end-to-end 5G network. As the number of containers grows, efficient management and orchestration of such containers becomes a challenging. Kubernetes¹³, an open-source container deployment and management systems, addresses this by offering extra services such as lifecycle management, updating and health check

⁸https://docs.ansible.com/ansible/latest/getting_started/introduction.html

⁹<https://docs.docker.com/get-started/docker-overview/>

¹⁰<https://hub.docker.com/>

¹¹<https://hub.docker.com/u/oaisoftwarealliance>

¹²<https://hub.docker.com/r/openverso/open5gs/tags>

¹³<https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/>

Fig. 1: 5G System Architecture and Interfaces [8]

monitoring and application recovery to realize flexibility and efficiency in 5G network slicing. Furthermore, Kubernetes also supports resource isolation capabilities through namespaces, which is key in network slicing isolation. In later sections, we leverage these capabilities to deploy network slices in the CN of the testbed proposed in this work.

In the context of 5G network slicing, infrastructure management can be done through Ansible, while containerized 5G NFs are orchestrated on Docker Engine. Automation is needed to manage complex Kubernetes application configuration and distribution. Helm¹⁴, the Kubernetes package manager, makes it possible to manage a Kubernetes application configuration file, install a new application that can be defined using a Helm chart, and update a Kubernetes application through the Helm command line tool. Therefore, in 5G network slicing, the life cycle of a network slice from slice creation, execution, monitoring and termination can be managed by the technology stack made up of Ansible, Docker, Kubernetes and Helm. We demonstrate this implementation in our work of building a simplified, low-cost network slicing-focused testbed in section IV.

III. RELATED WORKS

Large-scale city-wide testbeds with a focus on either next-generation wireless communication or network slicing have been implemented in [17] and [18]. Large-scale testbeds can be used for rigorous real-world deployments and evaluations. At the same time, there is a desire to test the specific low-level features and capabilities of novel designs and architectures of 5G networks to achieve the vision of

the 3GPP 5G system specifications [19], [20]. As such, prototyping systems that implement or are biased towards individual parts of the 5G of the mobile network architecture, such as the RAN, TN or CN, miss out on the opportunity to evaluate complex end-to-end multitenancy networks that evaluate implementations, such as network slicing [5].

The work by [7] implements 5GIIK, which is a small-scale testbed for E2E network slicing with the capability of management and orchestration of network resources. As much as they also use the cloud native philosophy to deploy their network slices, we view this work as an early contribution to the initial approaches of building a network slicing testbed. While this contribution is valuable, it is built on 4G LTE RAT using srsLTE¹⁵ and OAI CN and therefore does not align with 3GPP standards for defining and instantiating a network slice. The authors follow a hierarchical approach for creating slices, beginning with VNF Descriptors (VNFDs) as the first level, followed by Network Service Descriptors (NSDs) as the second level, and finally the Network Slice Instance Descriptor (NSID) which integrate the service instances to form a complete network slice.

Despite this VNF-focused description approach of creating an end-to-end network slice on this testbed, the 3GPP standard procedure of creating and adhering to 5G network slicing from identification and life cycle is not followed. Furthermore, we do not see 5G UE attach, and resource requests on the network for different slices that are available. This is an aspect that we demonstrate in our work and we employ standard identifiers, SST and SD values, to define, label, create, and monitor network slice instances.

¹⁴<https://helm.sh/>

¹⁵<https://github.com/srslte>

Fig. 2: Proposed 5G network slicing testbed architecture.

Recent work by [21] demonstrates the lack of true end-to-end network slicing. The authors implement network slices using open-source software. They use srsRAN for LTE implementation at the RAN and Open5GS as the core network. Their infrastructure is managed using OpenStack, Opendaylight (ODL), and Open-Source MANO (OSM). A B210 USRP SDR is used to act as a gNB and propagate wireless signals. Their implementation of network slices involves altering the placement of the UPF to achieve low-latency communication. Although they succeed in this, their approach does not show placement of traffic across the full path of an E2E network slice from the RAN to the CN, nor does it incorporate standardized slice identifiers such as SST and SD values. We can infer this because the RAN was implemented using srsRAN LTE software, which does not support 5G-NR and is unable to use SST and SD values for the authorization of access to the network.

The documentation by OAI¹⁶ on network slicing is the closest work related to this paper. We base our implementation on the basic Helm charts provided by the OAI project, which we extend and refined to ensure that there is total separation of the control plane and data plane in our network slice implementation. In addition, it is important to note that their network slice implementation involved two slices sharing an NRF, and one dedicated NRF for the third slice. The only common control functions shared by the three slices were the NSSF, AMF, UDM, UDR, and AUSF. Orchestration and

management of the slices is based on Docker compose, which in our work we implement total separation of control plane and data plane, where a dedicated data plane serves each slice with a shared control plane. This is done by translating the Docker Compose startup scripts into custom Helm charts on Kubernetes to manage the network slice infrastructure in our testbed.

This paper also presents an easy-to-follow step-by-step configuration to replicate this work in low-cost off-the-shelf computing devices for experimentation and research.

IV. TESTBED SETUP

The testbed consists of two desktops running Ubuntu 22.04. The machine hosting the core network features an Intel Core i7-9700F processor (8 cores), 24 GB of DDR4 RAM, an NVIDIA GeForce GT 710 GPU, and a 1 TB Seagate HDD. The RAN computer features an Intel Core i7-9700F processor (8 cores), 32 GB of DDR4 RAM, an NVIDIA GeForce GT 710 GPU, and a 1 TB Seagate HDD. The RAN machine runs the OAI RAN software suite that implements both the gNB and the nr-ue. We connect the two using an RF simulator. We did not use real UEs in this setup because, our primary objective was to evaluate an E2E network slicing deployment which extends beyond the basic connectivity testing. E2E connectivity tests using real UEs and different software suites from srsRAN, OAI and Open5GS have been evaluated in [4], [22], [23] and [24]. In these testbeds, the focus was not on evaluating network slicing but basic E2E connectivity, experience profiling and RAN optimization in [23] and [24], respectively, and the

¹⁶https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/cn5g/oai-cn5g-fed/-/blob/master/docs/DEPLOY_SA5G_SLICING.md

building of a framework for granular data collection and data set building in [22]. As we advance towards network slicing in this work, the limitation that made it difficult to use real UEs is UE capabilities for network slice selection using SST and SD values. Therefore, we evaluate the slicing-focused testbed using emulated UEs.

A. Initial Infrastructure Setup

We took the approach of setting up the infrastructure of the current testbed from bare metal to a basic setup with all software modules set and configured using the infrastructure as code paradigm with Ansible. The Ansible playbooks that we developed aimed to achieve automated RAN node setup for both emulated UE tests and real UE tests. To this end, we implemented playbooks that fetch, install and set up the USRP Hardware Driver (UHD) for SDR connections. On the RAN node, we implement a playbook that installs OAI RAN software suite, executes the CPU performance optimization scripts and launches the OAI gNB. For the CN node, we developed Ansible playbooks to allow the deployment of the OAI-CN software in a cloud native manner. The playbooks fetch and install Docker, Kubernetes with MicroK8s and Multus Meta CNI and HELM for package management. This Infrastructure-as-Code approach ensures that testbed setup is repeatable, consistent and Idempotent at all times. The Ansible playbook files used for this setup are publicly available in this Github repository ¹⁷

B. Network Configuration

This testbed was configured using OAI 5G NR and OAI-CN. The OAI RAN implementation (both the gNB and the UE) was based on an RF simulator to interconnect the two components. This is because of the limitation of real UEs that would allow the configuration of slice identifiers i.e., the SST and SD values. For the evaluation of our setup, we configured two slice identifiers: Slice 1 with SST 1, SD FFFFFFFF, and DNN oai, Slice 2 with SST 128, SD FFFFFFFF, and DNN test. These slice identifiers were cascaded from the UE configuration files through to the CN configuration files. While we relied on the Helm chart configuration files provided by OAI as a baseline, the modification made to customize this deployment in our testbed was to create three different Helm charts and accompanying configuration files that will be picked up whenever the charts were installed to implement and run this testbed. With all these Helm charts, we created different namespaces for the control plane network functions, and for the data plane serving each slice instance.

Connecting the RAN to CN is important for realizing both E2E network connectivity as well as E2E networks slice implementation. Since we have deployed the CN as Kubernetes pods, we needed to expose the AMF in the control plane and the UPF which constitutes the data plane in the CN. The other CN components are connected using the SBI interface implemented by the private addresses

within the Kubernetes network. To achieve this, we used Multus, a Container Network Interface (CNI) plugin which enabled the AMF and UPFs to bind to our local network addresses for reachability by the gNB. Accordingly, the N2 interface, N3 interfaces on UPF-slice 1 and UPF-Slice 2 were configured to bind to the Multus plugin in the "values.yaml" configuration files that each helm chart relied on during deployment. Furthermore, since the control plane and data planes we configured in this testbed had different namespaces, we were required to make adjustments in the configuration file to ensure that the NRF would easily register the two UPFs and SMFs that are in different namespaces and allow discovery of these network functions by the NSSF and the AMF during registration and network slice selection procedure. We achieved this by configuring the Go templates of the SMF and UPF. Talk about NSSF configuration to show allowed slices

V. RESULTS AND VALIDATION

In this section, we demonstrate the implementation of network slices on the testbed. This demonstration shows the process from slice request, slice selection and network slice implementation by the different associated network functions. As mentioned earlier, we have configured two UEs to connect to the network slices with the following IDs, SST 1 SD FFFFFFFF and DNN oai for Slice 1 and SST 128, SD FFFFFFFF and DNN test for Slice 2. The configurations for UE1 and UE2 are shown in Fig 4 and Fig 5.

A. RAN Network Slice Request to the CN

The initial request is sent to the AMF from the gNB by the UE to request a slice. In this case, the AMF will receive two slice requests, SST 1 SD FFFFFFFF for Slice 1 and SST 128, SD FFFFFFFF for Slice 2. These requests are then forwarded to the NSSF to ensure that these slices are configured as shown in the Fig. 6.

If these slices are not configured in the NSSF configuration file, the slices will not be allowed and the AMF will not process the UE request further. Moreover, an error will be returned to the UE. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the NSSF-AMF interaction log messages for slices that are correctly configured and allowed by the NSSF. The NSSF then responds to this NSSAI request from the AMF by checking if the requested slice by the UE is among the allowed slice in the CN. If these values match, the NSSF responds with a valid S-NSSAI for the NSI and Authorized network slice as shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

B. CN functions slice selection

It is important to note that in the CN configuration files, we explicitly configured SMF selection at the AMF. This means, the AMF, in conjunction with the NRF will select the appropriate SMF based on the S-NSSAI. In our case, since we have two slices configured in the network, we expect the AMF to select the appropriate SMF and send the PDU session setup request.

¹⁷<https://github.com/HumphreyDev/5G-CN-Slicing>

Fig. 3: Network slicing testbed implementation and architecture

```
uicc0 = {
imsi = "001010000000100";
key = "fec86ba6eb707ed08905757b1bb44b8f";
opc= "C42449363BBAD02B66D16BC975D77CC1";
dnn= "oai";
nssai_sst=1;
nssai_sd=0xffffffff;
}
```

Fig. 4: UE 1 slice and DNN configuration.

```
uicc0 = {
imsi = "001010000000101";
key = "fec86ba6eb707ed08905757b1bb44b8f";
opc= "C42449363BBAD02B66D16BC975D77CC1";
dnn= "test";
nssai_sst=128;
nssai_sd=0xffffffff;
}
```

Fig. 5: UE 2 slice and DNN configuration.

The SMF also engages in a UPF selection criteria based on the S-NSSAI information and slice request it gets from the AMF. And build a UPF graph. This selection based on SST 1 SD FFFFFFF and SST 128, SD FFFFFFF is shown in the Fig 9 and Fig 10.

To further verify that different SMFs were selected by the AMF for the two slices configured in the network, in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, the SMF URI is different for each selection procedure.

Slice 1 SMF IP address is 10.1.240.160 while Slice 2 SMF IP address is 10.1.240.133.

C. Network Slice Establishment

After SMF selection, the SMF sends the PDU session creation request to the appropriate UPF serving either the SST 1, SD FFFFFFF slice instance or the SST 128, SD FFFFFFF slice instance. Successful session establishment is confirmed by assigning an IP address to the UE from the

```
# Reference:- TS 29.531 R16.0.0., Section- 6.1.6 Data Model
info:
  version: 2.0.0
  description: OAI-NSSF Release v2.1.0
configuration:
  nsiInfoList:
    - snssai:
      sst: 1
      sd: 'FFFFFF'
    nsiInformationList:
      nrfId: http://oai-nrf:80/nrf-disc/v1/nf-instances
      nsiId: '100'
      nrfNfMgtUri: http://oai-nrf:80/nrf-nfm/v1/nf-instances
    - snssai:
      sst: 128
      sd: 'FFFFFF'
    nsiInformationList:
      nrfId: http://oai-nrf:80/nrf-disc/v1/nf-instances
      nsiId: '10'
  taiInfoList:
    - tai:
      plmnId:
        mcc: '001'
        mnc: '01'
        tac: '0x0001'
      supportedSnssaiList:
        - sst: 1
          sd: 'FFFFFF'
        - sst: 128
          sd: 'FFFFFF'
```

Fig. 6: Redacted NSSF configuration file

```
[nssf_sbi] [debug] QueryString: nf-type=AMF&nf-id=d3ee9c81-4472-4a7f-b2cd-8e653e13eb46&slice-info-request-for-pdu-session={*roamingIndication*}
[nssf_sbi] [info] Query_PARAM:NF_TYPE - AMF
[nssf_sbi] [info] Query_PARAM:Nf_ID - d3ee9c81-4472-4a7f-b2cd-8e653e13eb46
[nssf_app] [info] Query_PARAM slice-info-request-for-pdu-session - (*roamingIndication*:NON_ROAMING, *snssai*:{*sd*:'FFFFFF', *sst*:'1'})
[nssf_sbi] [info] NS Selection: Got a request with slice info for PDU Session, Instance ID: d3ee9c81-4472-4a7f-b2cd-8e653e13eb46
[nssf_app] [info] NS Selection: Handle case - PDU Session (HTTP_VERSION 2)
[nssf_app] [debug] Validating S-NSSAI for NSI
[nssf_app] [info] NS Selection: Authorized Network Slice Info Returned !!!
[nssf_app] [info] //
```

Fig. 7: AMF and NSSF Authorized Slice 1 Request and Response

subnet associated with the selected network slice instance. We demonstrate the UPF selection procedure for the different NSI in Fig 11 and Fig 12.

It is equally important to note that the UPFs selected by the SMF for each slice instance are assigned different IP addresses. This demonstrates UPF selection based on NSSAI (SST and SD pair) information provided by the UE to create a PDU session. The UPF serving slice 1 is on IP address 10.1.240.174 while the UPF serving slice 2 is on IP address 10.1.240.153.

In 5G networks, after the successful authentication which includes network slice NSSAI verification, the SMF triggers session establishment by assigning IP addresses to the UE. In this work, to further illustrate resource and traffic isolation in the network slices configured, we configured the different SMFs to assign IP addresses to the different UEs with different SST, SD and DNN values. The subnet configured SST 1, SD FFFFFFFF and DNN oai was 12.1.1.0/24, while SST 128, SD FFFFFFFF and DNN test was 14.1.1.0/24. These configurations were passed as config files in the different Helm charts that deployed the SMF and UPF data planes for slice 1 and slice 2. Thereafter, the associated GTPU tunnels are created between

```
[nssf_app] [info] //
[nssf_sbi] [debug] Received request for NS Selection - (HTTP_VERSION 2)
[nssf_app] [debug] QueryString: nf-type=AMF&nf-id=d3ee9c81-4472-4a7f-b2cd-8e653e13eb46&slice-info-request-for-pdu-session={*roamingIndication*}
[nssf_sbi] [info] Query_PARAM:Nf_ID - d3ee9c81-4472-4a7f-b2cd-8e653e13eb46
[nssf_sbi] [info] Query_PARAM slice-info-request-for-pdu-session - (*roamingIndication*:NON_ROAMING, *snssai*:{*sd*:'FFFFFF', *sst*:'128'})
[nssf_app] [info] NS Selection: Got a request with slice info for PDU Session, Instance ID: d3ee9c81-4472-4a7f-b2cd-8e653e13eb46
[nssf_app] [info] NS Selection: Handle case - PDU Session (HTTP_VERSION 2)
[nssf_app] [info] NS Selection: Authorized Network Slice Info Returned !!!
[nssf_app] [info] //
```

Fig. 8: AMF and NSSF Authorized Slice 2 Request and Response

```
[amf_sbi] [debug] S-NSSAI is not matched for SMF profile
[amf_sbi] [debug] S-NSSAI [SST-1, SD-FFFFFF] is matched for SMF profile
[amf_sbi] [debug] NFDiscovey, SMF Info: Addr 10.1.240.160, Port 80, API Version v1
[amf_sbi] [debug] Decoded PTI for PDU Session Establishment Request(0x1)
[amf_sbi] [debug] Handle PDU Session Establishment Request (SUPI imsi-001010000000100, PDU Session ID 10)
[nssf_app] [debug] Validating S-NSSAI for NSI
[amf_sbi] [debug] SMF URI: 10.1.240.160/nsmf-pdusession/v1/sm-contexts
```

Fig. 9: SMF selection by AMF for Slice 1

the gNB and the UPF through N3. The UEs will use their respective IP address to communicate and send traffic to different subnets in the network. Figures 13 and 14 show the different subnets the two UEs belong to.

VI. LESSONS LEARNED

From the implementation of this testbed, several key lessons were learned. First, while open-source software such as OAI and Open5GS provides the foundation for 5G slicing experimentation, their documentation and reference implementations often lack sufficient detail for end-to-end slice realisation, requiring significant customization. Second, Infrastructure-as-Code approaches such as Ansible and container orchestration with Kubernetes and Helm greatly improved repeatability, consistency, and modularity, but required careful tuning of configuration files, namespaces, and templates to ensure proper NF registration and discovery. Third, achieving strict separation of control and data planes proved essential for validating slice isolation, though it introduced additional complexity in network configuration and management. Finally, the absence of real UEs with slice-aware capabilities (SST and SD configurations) remains a limitation, underscoring the importance of emulation in early-stage prototyping while highlighting the gap toward fully standard-compliant E2E slicing evaluation.

VII. FUTURE DIRECTION

Future work will extend this testbed in several directions. First, we plan to incorporate real 5G UEs with slice-aware capabilities to validate slice selection and service differentiation beyond emulated environments. Second, integration of the transport network/backhaul will be explored to achieve full RAN-TN-CN E2E slicing. Third, we plan to integrate advanced orchestration frameworks such as Open Source Mano¹⁸ will be evaluated on top of our Kubernetes-Helm stack to enable dynamic slice life cycle management, SLA enforcement, and automated scaling. Furthermore, benchmarking the performance of uRLLC, eMBB, and mMTC slice types under varying workloads will provide quantitative insights into resource isolation and QoS guarantees. Finally, we aim to eventually extend this

¹⁸<https://www.etsi.org/technologies/open-source-mano>

```

[smf_sbi] [debug] S-NSSAI [SST= 128, SD =FFFFFF] is matched for SMF profile
[smf_sbi] [debug] NFDiscovery, SMF Info: Addr 10.1.240.133, Port 80, API Version v1
[smf_sbi] [debug] Decoded PTI for PDUSESSIONEstablishmentRequest(0x1)
[smf_sbi] [debug] Handle PDU Session Establishment Request (SUP1 imsi=00101000000101, PDU Session ID 10)
[smf_sbi] [debug] SMF URI: 10.1.240.153:80/nsmf-pdusession/v1/sm-contexts

```

Fig. 10: SMF selection by AMF for Slice 2

```

[2025-09-18 05:28:11.580] [smf_app] [debug] Selection Criteria: - UPF Selection Criteria
+ ssnai:
- sst:.....: 1
- sd:.....: FFFFFFF
+ DNN:.....: oai

[2025-09-18 05:28:11.580] [smf_app] [debug] UPF 10.1.240.174 serves SSSAI
- ssnai:
+ sst:.....: 1
+ sd:.....: FFFFFFF

[2025-09-18 05:28:11.580] [smf_app] [debug] Successfully added UPF graph edge for 10.1.240.174: - UPF Graph Edge
+ Interface Type.....: N6
+ NWI:.....: No
+ UpLink.....: Yes
- UPF Graph Edge
+ Interface Type.....: N3
+ NWI:.....: No
+ UpLink.....: No
- UPF Graph Edge
+ Interface Type.....: N6
+ NWI:.....: No
+ UpLink.....: Yes

```

Fig. 11: UPF selection Slice 1

```

[2025-09-18 09:27:06.329] [smf_app] [debug] Selection Criteria: - UPF Selection Criteria
+ ssnai:
- sst:.....: 128
- sd:.....: FFFFFFF
+ DNN:.....: test

[2025-09-18 09:27:06.329] [smf_app] [debug] UPF 10.1.240.153 serves SSSAI
- ssnai:
+ sst:.....: 128
+ sd:.....: FFFFFFF

[2025-09-18 09:27:06.329] [smf_app] [debug] Successfully added UPF graph edge for 10.1.240.153: - UPF Graph Edge
+ Interface Type.....: N6
+ NWI:.....: No
+ UpLink.....: Yes
- UPF Graph Edge
+ Interface Type.....: N3
+ NWI:.....: No
+ UpLink.....: No
- UPF Graph Edge
+ Interface Type.....: N6
+ NWI:.....: No
+ UpLink.....: Yes

```

Fig. 12: UPF selection Slice 1

```

4: oaitun_ue1: <POINTOPOINT,NOARP,UP,LOWER_UP> mtu 1500 qdisc fq_codel state UNKNOWN group default qlen 500
link/none
inet 12.1.1.2/24 scope global oaitun_ue1
valid_lft forever preferred_lft forever
inets fa89:448f:fe5d:4bb3:6180/64 scope link stable-privacy
valid_lft forever preferred_lft forever
van@ran-PP0AR370:~$

```

Fig. 13: UE 1 PDU session IP address allocation

```

5: oaitun_ue1: <POINTOPOINT,NOARP,UP,LOWER_UP> mtu 1500 qdisc fq_codel state UNKNOWN group default qlen 500
link/none
inet 14.1.1.2/24 scope global oaitun_ue1
valid_lft forever preferred_lft forever
inets fa89:448f:fe5d:4bb3:6180/64 scope link stable-privacy
valid_lft forever preferred_lft forever
van@ran-PP0AR370:~$

```

Fig. 14: UE 2 PDU session IP address allocation

testbed to multi-site or federated deployments across Africa, enabling collaborative and Afrocentric/localised research and experimentation on 5G and beyond networks in low-cost, resource-constrained settings. Specifically, we plan to extend this work to a contribution in the DIGITAFRICA project¹⁹ that aims to design a Pan Africa led research infrastructure in digital sciences. This work on network slicing targets one of the blueprints that will be developed in DIGITAFRICA for 5G and 6G experimentation modeling the SLICES-RIPost-5G blueprint²⁰.

¹⁹<https://www.digitafrica.eu/>

²⁰<https://doc.slices-ri.eu/BlueprintServices/beyond5G/beyond5G.html>

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a low-cost, cloud-native 5G testbed for end-to-end network slicing. By extending OAI's reference setup with custom Helm charts, we achieved control-data plane separation, slice instantiation, and traffic isolation using SST and SD identifiers. The testbed demonstrates that advanced slicing can be realized on off-the-shelf hardware, offering a practical platform for experimentation and capacity building. Future work will integrate real slice-aware UEs and extend slicing to the transport domain.

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